

Faith as Fostering Immune System: A Psycho-Spiritual Perspective

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Covid-19 has brought us face to face with the ultimate reality of life, that is survival. This robust virus, like spirituality, does not adhere to the boundaries of race, caste, ethnicity, religion, language, age, education and expertise. It enters all with the speed of breath and enslaves the respiratory system of any human. It crawls slowly and steadily. It advances like cancer and makes the person vulnerable to any type of emergency and failure. So, the ultimate goal of the virus is to defeat survival and life. Therefore, it is advised by all the statutory bodies to avoid all contacts with the people infected with virus and follow strictly the social distancing. Right now, it may be a very painful process for many to be locked inside the house. It can drive people crazy and make them totally helpless. Peeks of despair can be seen and felt not only among those who do not have day to day resources for survival, but also, among those who have enough but do not know how to manage their time without keeping up to the previously conditioned daily routine.

Covid-19 and Immune System

There are two major avenues of difficulty that arise with this pandemic. One created by the Covid-19 and another by the parallel process of being locked inside the house with social distancing. Both create stress and perhaps, for many it is a time of chronic stress. Chronic stress has two major consequences. It suppresses the immune system,¹ and at the same time, creates emotional upheavals

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and a negative mood.² Psychologists differentiate between two types of stresses, viz., the acute or chronic. The former helps in developing “adaptive processes for potential adverse environments,”³ and the latter damages the ability to adapt, thus, opening the system to various malfunctions and diseases. In the living beings, chronic stress elicits more circulation of cortisol, adrenaline and nonadrenaline.⁴ These hormones trigger off the fight or flight reaction. As a consequence, breath and heart rate, glucose level in the blood, and the circulation of the blood in the skeletal muscles increases to more than tolerable levels.⁵ Such a status renders the immune system weak and makes the whole person more vulnerable to the outside viral attacks. After scrutinizing various studies, Cohen attempts to make a connection between stress and upper respiratory infections.⁶ Of course, he is not referring to covid-19, yet, the assumption that immune system can be weakened because of the chronic stress, stands true.

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Drawing from the Infinite Resource of Faith

Present lock-down scenario has created enough stress to create an imbalance among the families, social and economic situations. Being at home without any productive work and too

much of time on hand can create a lot of stress. For some it could create acute stress and for others chronic. Not able to move out of the house to gain essential commodities, exercise, social meetings and employment has the possibilities of creating more chronic stress. Such condition itself is enough to trigger negative emotions and pessimism leading to helplessness and despair.

In these trying times everyone may look for a quick-heal process, yet, looking at the world pandemic, one can easily judge that the end of such attack is not in the close vicinity as envisaged. Such a perception also can create a lot of stress. Watching TV and the news makes us wonder whether we shall overcome such a crisis with our own potential and medical help. Here is where, Koevig intervenes and suggests that we have a common infinite resource and that is our faith, or spirituality or religion. He suggests that religion provides “a more positive, optimistic worldview,” and thus, improves coping mechanisms with acute or chronic stress,” and thereby ameliorates “the effects that stress has on the immune system.”⁷ He also patronizes a belief that “what people believe, think, and feel may have a direct impact on neuroendocrine and immune function-systems that play a vital role in warding off disease and speeding recovery from illness.”⁸ These are powerful beliefs and tested by scientific research. Further, Solomon believes that faith can activate the brain-psych-body balance, particularly during the times of chronic stress and strengthen the adaptive coping styles coupled with developing positive emotions.⁹ Therefore, we have hope in the common resource that we enjoy every day, our religion and spirituality. It can help us build a healthy relationship with self, God, others and the cosmos and fortify the immune system.¹⁰ Religion provides us with the ways of grasping coherently

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with meaning of life. It helps us to engage in rituals and symbolic expressions. It helps us to gain means and methods to awaken the divine and let the divine reign in us even in the most difficult situations of life.

Ways of Dealing with Stress

Let us look at some of the concrete ways of dealing with stress especially in the present situation of Covid-19.

Chronic stress begins with perception. Clarity in perception as regards Covid-19 can help us do away with unnecessary stress. Most of the news items are telling us that covid-19 is a deadly virus. We need to accept that it is so. It is transmitted through the droplets. So care has to be taken that we wash our hands regularly, keep a safe distance from others, and try not to touch the facial region too often as and when we are outside the safe precincts. In many cases, people have been able to come back to normality after being affected. So there is hope for those who can retain and accelerate the inner strength of their immune system.

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Secondly, as psychoneuroimmunologists (PNIs) are suggesting, we can begin to develop a positive relationship with God. Understand God’s inner nature which is eternal and infinite love. Surrender ourselves to God, and allow that eternal and infinite nature to come down into us and dwell among us. Prayerful practices such as reading the Scriptures, rosary, Jesus prayer, and meditative reflection can help in developing a personal relationship with God and allow God to be the centre of our lives.

Healthy conversations and sharings involving one’s inner thoughts, feelings, emotions, and future plans could be promoted. It might be very beneficial to help one another recognize each others’ contribution towards growth in all.

Thirdly, PNIs are also suggesting that we need to rebuild our family and social relations. In the normal times family and social relations take a backseat. Employment and job responsibilities take the front seat. Covid-19 has reversed the situation for a while. We can use such an opportunity to rebuild our family relations. Healthy conversations and sharings involving one's inner thoughts, feelings, emotions, and future plans could be promoted. It might be very beneficial to help one another recognize each others' contribution towards growth in all. They could respect each other's uniqueness and appreciate the differences. One of the important elements that might help in rebuilding relationships is the practice of non-judgementality. Begin with one's own thoughts and feelings. View and observe them non-judgementally. With practice we will be able to refrain from acting on those automatic thoughts and emotions. When we stop acting on them then we don't react. It is called the art of self-regulation.

Fourthly, being at home after a long gap and for a long period time has the possibility of triggering off old memories and old experiences which we nurture in our hearts. Some could be positive and some negative. Often negative ones will exert more power in accelerating and retaining the chronic stress and thus, make the system vulnerable. Present situation might be a God-given opportunity to process the old negative experiences through the lens of God and forgive people, especially those who have demeaned, insulted, rejected and hurt us most. Such reconciliation can strengthen the immune system.

Fifthly, we need to take care of our bodies. They need nourishment and exercise. PNI's are suggesting that moderate intensity physical exercise can increase relaxation and strengthen the immune

system.¹¹ Research in this area suggest that certain amount of regularity and consistency helps in stimulating anti-inflammatory and the immune system of the body.¹²

Finally, we are all human beings in this big global village. Helping one another and encouraging one another might go a long way in rebuilding ourselves. Therefore, moving out of ourselves in kindness, generosity, mercy and compassion towards those who are suffering more than us due to joblessness, lack of essential commodities, injustice and poverty has the power to strengthen our communal ties over against the common enemy, covid-19. We could generously and wholeheartedly enter into such ventures that will help others to gain a chance to survive this pandemic.

Conclusion

There could be other methods and more effective than which suggested in the article. When we share them with others reflectively and respectfully, we all gain the benefits of such methods and together all can fight the Covid-19 with internal and external strengths. Our common faith could be the great resource for our wholeness and healing.

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¹ Eduardo Vignoto Fernandes, Celio Estanislau and Emerson José Venancio, "Moderate Intensity Physical Exercise: Psychoneuroimmunological Aspects," *Rev Bras Med Esporte* vol.24 no.5 São Paulo (Sept./Oct. 2018): 395, <https://doi.org/10.1590/1517-869220182405185533>.

² Antonia C. Lyons and Kerry Chamberlain, *Health Psychology: A Critical Introduction* (Cambridge: Cambridge University, 2005), 154-5.

³ Qing Yan, *Psychoneuroimmunology: Systems Biology Approaches to Mind-Body Medicine* (Switzerland: Springer International, 2016), 11.

⁴ Eduardo Vignoto Fernandes, Celio Estanislau and Emerson José Venancio, "Moderate Intensity Physical Exercise: Psychoneuroimmunological Aspects," *Rev Bras Med Esporte* vol.24 no.5 São Paulo (Sept./Oct. 2018): 396.

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- ⁵ Eduardo Vignoto et al, "Moderate Intensity Physical Exercise: Psychoneuroimmunological Aspects," *Rev Bras Med Esporte* vol.24 no.5 São Paulo (Sept./Oct. 2018): 396.
- ⁶ Sheldon Cohen, "Psychosocial Stress, Social Networks and Susceptibility to Infection," in *The Link Between Religion and Health: Psychoneuroimmunology and Faith factor*, eds. Harold G. Koenig and Harvey J. Cohen (New York: Oxford, 2002), 101-16.
- ⁷ Harold G. Koenig, "The Connection Between Psychoneuroimmunology and Religion," in *The Link Between Religion and Health: Psychoneuroimmunology and Faith factor*, eds. Harold G. Koenig and Harvey J. Cohen (New York: Oxford, 2002), 22.
- ⁸ Harold G. Koenig, "The Connection", 27.
- ⁹ George Solomon, "The Developmental History of Psychoneuroimmunology," in *The Link Between Religion and Health: Psychoneuroimmunology and Faith factor*, eds. Harold G. Koenig and Harvey J. Cohen (New York: Oxford, 2002), 39.
- ¹⁰ Warren S. Brown, "Psychoneuroimmunology and Western Religious Tradition," in *The Link Between Religion and Health: Psychoneuroimmunology and Faith factor*, eds. Harold G. Koenig and Harvey J. Cohen (New York: Oxford, 2002), 271.
- ¹¹ Fernandes et al "Moderate," 398.
- ¹² Fernandes et al "Moderate," 396.